

ROSIE

D8.5: Events

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ABSTRACT:	D8.5: Events contains a list of relevant events in which ROSiE consortium members plan to participate during the 1 st year of the project (March-December 2021). These events are not necessarily events organized by ROSiE, but events related to Research Ethics, Research Integrity and Research Management. At these events ROSiE members will present ROSiE or in other ways seek to raise awareness of the project. This deliverable will be updated each year by NTUA. Updated versions of D8.5 Events will be submitted in M12, M24, and M36.
Keyword List:	n.a.

Consortium:

No.	Role	Name	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	ÖSTERREICHISCHE AGENTUR FÜR WISSENSCHAFTLICHE INTEGRITÄT	OeAWI	Austria
3.	Partner	VEREIN DER EUROPAEISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN	ECSA	Germany
4.	Partner	EUREC OFFICE GUG	EUREC	Germany
5.	Partner	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAINVALTUUSKUNNASTA	TSV	Finland
6.	Partner	HAUT CONSEIL DE L'EVALUATION DE LA RECHERCHE ET DE L'ENSEIGNEMENT SUPÉRIEUR	HCERES	France
7.	Partner	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	INRAE	France
8.	Partner	NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NTUA	Greece
9.	Partner	UNIVERSIDADE CATÓLICA PORTUGUESA	UCP	Portugal
10.	Partner	LATVIJAS UNIVERSITĀTE	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	TARTU ÜLIKOOL	UT	Estonia
12.	Partner	UNIVERSITETET I SOROST-NORGE	USN	Norway

N o.	Event	Dates	Venue	City	Country	Name of attendee/ Entity	Related HYBRIDA WP	Reason for participation	Title of contribution (if applicable)	Type of contribution (Oral presentation, Poster presentation)	Comments
1.	Open Science Workshop 'Innovationen im Gesundheitswesen'	27.05. 2021	Online event	Vienna	Austria	T. Konach	WP5	Member of the national RRI-platform	-	Oral presentation during the workshop session(<i>tbc.</i>)	Introducing the overall goals of ROSiE, and specifically tasks of the WP5
2.	The World Conferences on Research Integrity	29.05-02.06. 2021	Online event	-	-	N. Foeger	WP5, WP8	Member of the Governing Board of the WCIR	-	Participation in the digital event	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project
3.	FAIR Festival	21-23.06. 2021	Online event	-	-	N. Foeger/ T. Konach	WP5, WP8	Introducing the goals of ROSiE, and specifically of WP5	-	Participation in GO BUILD – GO TRAIN – GO CHANGE session (<i>tbc.</i>)	Opportunity to tell the participants about the development in the project and to get in touch with the Implementation Teams of the GoFair Initiative
4.	Digital Humanities Oxford Summer School 2021	12-15.07. 2021	Online event	-	-	T. Konach	WP5, WP8	Introducing the ROSiE-project, the work in WP5 and possible links to the DH community	Tbc.	Oral presentation and an Q&A session(<i>tbc.</i>)	Introducing the goals of ROSiE, and specifically those of WP5; fostering synergies between the

											project and the DH community
5.	Open Science Fair	20-24.09.2021	Online event	-	-	T. Konach, N. Foeger	WP5	Presenting the WP5 within one the conference's main topics: <i>Interdisciplinary collaborations: Networks, services, methods: Open science and data policies</i>	Tbc.	Poster presentation (<i>tbc.</i>)	Introducing the project to the international Open Science community and to the general public
6.	Vienna Days of Academic Integrity/ Wiener Tage der Akademischen Integrität	22-25.09.2021	Tbc.	Vienna	Austria	N. Foeger/ T. Konach	WP8	Annual presentation of OeAWI at the Exhibition Area	Tbc.	Poster presentation (<i>tbc.</i>)	Introducing the project to the general public
7.	ENRIO Conference	27-29.09.2021	Online event	-	-	N. Foeger/ T. Konach	WP8, WP5	Member of ENRIO	Tbc.	Tbc.	Introducing the project and its newest developments
8.	Open-Access-Days/ Open-Access-Tag	27-29.09.2021	Online event	Vienna	Austria	T. Konach	WP8, WP5	Ongoing cooperation with the organizer – the Open Science Network Austria	Tbc.	Poster presentation (<i>Tbc.</i>)	Introducing the project to the national Open Science community and to the general public

9.	Lectures, workshops and training activities	On-going	Virtual/in-person	-	Austria and abroad	N. Foeger	WP8	Lectures, workshops and training activities	-	-	Presentation of the project in each lecture, workshop or other training activity (permanent slide in each presentation)
10	ENRIO member's corner	24 March 2021	Online event	-	-	Panagiotis Kavouras	WP8	Communicating the initiation of ROSIE	ROSIE: Responsible Open Science in Europe	Oral presentation	An interesting discussion followed the presentation
11	University of Latvia Science Night	30 April 2021	Online event		Latvia	Signe Mezińska	WP8	Panel discussion on citizen science	Ethical aspects of citizen science	Participation in a panel discussion	
12	ENRIO2021 Congress	27-29 September 2021	Online event	-	-	Olivier Le Gall (INRAE) Panagiotis Kavouras (NTUA) Etc.	WP8	Olivier: Invited speaker	Olivier: Bibliodiversity, open science and research integrity	Olivier: Oral presentation	Olivier can/will briefly introduce ROSIE if no dedicated talk is programmed
13	American Society for Bioethics and Humanities	13-15 October 2021	Online event		USA	Søren Holm	General about ROSIE	Søren Holm: Speaker	Søren Holm: Does Open Science create an open season for new types of research misconduct?	Søren Holm: Oral presentation	Submitted, but not yet accepted (decision July 2021)

